

A Comparative Study of Oral Clonidine (150mcg) Vs Oral Gabapentin (300mg) as Premedication on Intraoperative Hemodynamics and Incidence of Post-Operative Nausea and Vomiting and Post-Operative Pain Relief in Patients Undergoing Middle Ear Surgeries

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Abstract:

Background: Intraoperative hemodynamic changes, post-operative nausea and vomiting (PONV), and post-operative pain are common challenges in middle ear surgeries. This study compared the effects of oral clonidine and gabapentin as premedication on these parameters.

Objectives: The study aimed to evaluate and compare the effects of a single dose of oral clonidine (150mcg) and oral gabapentin (300mg) on intraoperative hemodynamics, PONV incidence, post-operative pain relief, and adverse effects in patients undergoing middle ear surgeries.

Methods: A prospective, randomized, double-blind study was conducted on 180 ASA I and II patients divided into three groups (n=60 each): clonidine, gabapentin, and placebo. The study drugs were administered one hour before surgery. Intraoperative hemodynamics, PONV incidence, post-operative pain scores (VAS), and adverse effects were recorded.

Results: Clonidine and gabapentin significantly reduced heart rate and blood pressure compared to the placebo group (p<0.05). PONV incidence was significantly lower in the clonidine and gabapentin groups (p<0.05), with clonidine showing better results. Post-operative VAS scores were significantly lower in the clonidine and gabapentin groups (p<0.05), with clonidine providing better pain relief. No significant adverse effects were noted.

Conclusions: Premedication with oral clonidine (150mcg) or gabapentin (300mg) effectively attenuates intraoperative hemodynamic changes, reduces PONV incidence, and provides better post-operative pain relief compared to placebo in patients undergoing middle ear surgeries. Clonidine showed superior results compared to gabapentin.

Keywords: Clonidine, Gabapentin, Premedication, Middle ear surgery, Hemodynamics, PONV, Post-operative pain.

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Introduction

Middle ear surgeries, including tympanoplasty, mastoidectomy, and stapedectomy, are commonly performed otologic procedures that aim to restore hearing and treat chronic ear conditions [1]. However, these surgeries are associated with significant intraoperative hemodynamic changes, postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV), and postoperative pain, which can negatively impact patient recovery and satisfaction [2].

Intraoperative hemodynamic changes during middle ear surgeries can be attributed to the stimulation of the trigeminal nerve and the vestibulocochlear nerve during surgical manipulation, leading to a sympathetic response

[3]. This response manifests as an increase in heart rate and blood pressure, which can be detrimental to patients with preexisting cardiovascular conditions [4]. Moreover, the use of general anesthesia and the need for a bloodless surgical field necessitate the use of controlled hypotension, which can further exacerbate these hemodynamic changes [5].

PONV is a common and distressing complication following middle ear surgeries, with an incidence ranging from 40% to 80% [6]. The etiology of PONV is multifactorial, involving patient-related factors (female gender, non-smoking status, history of motion sickness), anesthesia-related factors (use

of volatile anesthetics, opioids), and surgery-related factors (duration of surgery, middle ear manipulation) [7]. PONV can lead to delayed recovery, prolonged hospital stay, and increased healthcare costs [8].

Postoperative pain is another significant concern following middle ear surgeries, particularly in the early postoperative period [9]. Inadequate pain control can result in patient discomfort, delayed mobilization, and an increased risk of complications such as deep vein thrombosis and pulmonary embolism [10]. Opioids are commonly used for postoperative pain management; however, they are associated with side effects such as sedation, respiratory depression, and PONV [11].

Premedication with drugs that have anxiolytic, analgesic, and antiemetic properties has been proposed as a strategy to mitigate these perioperative challenges [12]. Clonidine, an α_2 -adrenergic agonist, has been studied as a premedication agent due to its ability to provide sedation, analgesia, and hemodynamic stability [13]. It has been shown to reduce anesthetic requirements, attenuate the stress response to surgical stimuli, and decrease postoperative pain and opioid consumption [14,15].

Gabapentin, an anticonvulsant drug, has also gained attention as a premedication agent in recent years [16]. It has been reported to possess anxiolytic, analgesic, and antiemetic properties [17]. Preoperative administration of gabapentin has been shown to reduce postoperative pain scores, opioid consumption, and the incidence of PONV in various surgical settings [18,19].

While both clonidine and gabapentin have been individually studied as premedication agents, there is limited literature directly comparing their effects in the context of middle ear surgeries. This study aims to evaluate and compare the effects of oral clonidine (150mcg) and oral gabapentin (300mg) as premedication on intraoperative hemodynamics, PONV incidence, and postoperative pain relief in patients undergoing middle ear surgeries. We hypothesize that premedication with either clonidine or gabapentin will result in better hemodynamic stability, reduced PONV incidence, and improved postoperative pain control compared to placebo. The findings of this study may help optimize premedication strategies to enhance patient outcomes and satisfaction in this surgical population.

Aims and Objectives

The primary aim of this study was to evaluate and compare the effects of a single dose of oral clonidine (150mcg) and oral gabapentin (300mg) as premedication on intraoperative hemodynamics, postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) incidence, and postoperative pain relief in patients

undergoing middle ear surgeries. The secondary objective was to assess the occurrence of any adverse effects related to the study drugs.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: This prospective, randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study was conducted in the Department of Anesthesiology and Critical Care at a tertiary care center over a period of 24 months, after obtaining institutional ethical committee clearance and informed written consent from all patients.

Sample Size and Randomization: The sample size was calculated using the formula for comparison of means between three groups, with an alpha error of 0.05 and a beta error of 0.2 (power of 80%). A total of 180 patients were included and randomly allocated to three groups (60 patients in each group) using computer-generated randomization. Group 1 received oral clonidine 150mcg, Group 2 received oral gabapentin 300mg, and Group 3 received a placebo (vitamin C tablet) as premedication.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria: Patients aged 15-65 years, of both sexes, belonging to the American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status I and II, and scheduled for elective middle ear surgical procedures under general anesthesia with an expected duration of 120-240 minutes were included in the study. Patients who refused to participate, had ASA physical status III or higher, a history of seizure disorder, allergy to the study drugs, severe bradyarrhythmia, coronary artery disease, Raynaud's or other peripheral occlusive diseases, cardio-respiratory pathology, low cardiac output, impaired left ventricular function, psychiatric illness, or renal impairment were excluded from the study.

Study Intervention and Anesthetic Management: All patients were assessed preoperatively and their baseline heart rate and non-invasive blood pressure were recorded. The study drugs were administered orally one hour before surgery according to the group allocation. In the operating room, standard anesthetic techniques were followed. Anesthesia was induced with intravenous thiopentone sodium (4-6 mg/kg) or propofol (2-3 mg/kg) and fentanyl (1-2 mcg/kg). Vecuronium (0.1mg/kg) or atracurium (0.5mg/kg) was used for orotracheal intubation. Anesthesia was maintained with an oxygen-air mixture (50:50) and isoflurane or sevoflurane, maintaining a minimum alveolar concentration (MAC) of 0.8-1%. Intraoperative analgesia was supplemented with fentanyl boluses of 25-50 mcg as needed.

Data Collection and Outcome Measures: Intraoperative hemodynamic parameters, including heart rate, systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, end-tidal carbon dioxide (EtCO₂), and

peripheral oxygen saturation (SpO₂), were monitored and recorded every 3 minutes during the surgery and in the postoperative period. The incidence of PONV was assessed in the immediate postoperative period and at 2-6 hours and 6-12 hours postoperatively. Postoperative pain intensity was evaluated using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) in the immediate postoperative period and at 2-6 hours and 6-12 hours postoperatively. Any rescue analgesic administered was recorded. The occurrence of adverse effects or complications related to the study drugs, such as hypotension, bradycardia, atrioventricular block, headache, dry mouth, hallucinations, depression, tremors, nystagmus, nervousness, or amnesia, was also noted and managed accordingly.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical software. Quantitative data were presented as mean \pm standard deviation and compared using the analysis of variance (ANOVA) test. Qualitative data were presented as frequency and percentage and analyzed using the Chi-square test. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The study included a total of 180 patients, with 60 patients randomly allocated to each of the three groups: clonidine (Group 1), gabapentin (Group 2), and placebo (Group 3). The demographic characteristics of the patients were comparable across the three groups (Table 1). The mean age of the patients was 35.7 ± 12.02 years, 35.3 ± 13.23 years, and 34.7 ± 10.74 years in Groups 1, 2, and 3, respectively ($p > 0.05$). The distribution of male and female patients was similar in all groups, with no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$). The mean weight of the patients was also comparable, with 67.1 ± 10.43 kg, 65.4 ± 11.21 kg, and 63.3 ± 11.63 kg in Groups 1, 2, and 3, respectively ($p > 0.05$). The majority of the patients belonged to ASA Grade I, with no significant difference in the distribution of ASA grades between the groups ($p > 0.05$). The presence of comorbidities was noted in 33.3%, 20%, and 16.7% of the patients in Groups 1, 2, and 3, respectively, but this difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

The intraoperative hemodynamic parameters were assessed and compared between the groups (Table

2). The baseline heart rate (HR) was significantly different among the groups ($p < 0.05$), with lower values in Group 1 (75.35 ± 5.99 beats/min) and Group 2 (74.82 ± 6.62 beats/min) compared to Group 3 (71.07 ± 8.59 beats/min). At induction, the HR was significantly lower in Group 1 (70.61 ± 5.56 beats/min) compared to Group 2 (75.95 ± 5.91 beats/min) and Group 3 (81.90 ± 6.47 beats/min) ($p < 0.05$). The baseline systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) were similar across the groups ($p > 0.05$). However, at induction, SBP was significantly lower in Group 1 (102.17 ± 10.36 mmHg) compared to Group 2 (117.98 ± 9.86 mmHg) and Group 3 (108.00 ± 10.68 mmHg) ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, DBP at induction was significantly lower in Group 1 (66.82 ± 7.67 mmHg) compared to Group 2 (73.23 ± 7.42 mmHg) and Group 3 (78.38 ± 4.74 mmHg) ($p < 0.05$).

The incidence of postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) was evaluated at different time points (Table 3). In the immediate postoperative period, PONV incidence was significantly lower in Group 1 (0.92 ± 0.38) and Group 2 (1.07 ± 0.25) compared to Group 3 (3.72 ± 1.83) ($p < 0.05$). Similarly, during the 0-6 hours postoperative period, PONV incidence remained significantly lower in Group 1 (0.55 ± 0.50) and Group 2 (1.00 ± 0.10) compared to Group 3 (2.78 ± 1.59) ($p < 0.05$). In the 6-12 hours postoperative period, PONV incidence was significantly lower in Group 1 (0.03 ± 0.18) compared to Group 2 (0.95 ± 0.22) and Group 3 (1.17 ± 0.38) ($p < 0.05$).

Postoperative pain intensity was assessed using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) at different time points (Table 4). In the immediate postoperative period, VAS scores were significantly lower in Group 1 (2.23 ± 1.10) and Group 2 (2.68 ± 1.07) compared to Group 3 (4.55 ± 1.53) ($p < 0.05$). During the 0-6 hours postoperative period, VAS scores remained significantly lower in Group 1 (2.65 ± 0.73) and Group 2 (2.98 ± 0.70) compared to Group 3 (4.10 ± 0.84) ($p < 0.05$). In the 6-12 hours postoperative period, VAS scores were significantly lower in Group 1 (1.58 ± 0.56) and Group 2 (1.95 ± 0.59) compared to Group 3 (3.03 ± 0.76) ($p < 0.05$).

No significant adverse effects or complications related to the study drugs were observed in any of the groups throughout the study period.

Table 1: Patient Demographics

Variable	Group 1 (Clonidine)	Group 2 (Gabapentin)	Group 3 (Placebo)	p-value
Age (years)	35.7 ± 12.02	35.3 ± 13.23	34.7 ± 10.74	> 0.05
Sex (M/F)	39/21	37/23	42/18	> 0.05
Weight (kg)	67.1 ± 10.43	65.4 ± 11.21	63.3 ± 11.63	> 0.05
ASA Grade (I/II)	45/15	44/16	51/9	> 0.05
Comorbidities (n, %)	20 (33.3%)	12 (20%)	10 (16.7%)	> 0.05

Table 2: Intraoperative Hemodynamics

Variable	Group 1 (Clonidine)	Group 2 (Gabapentin)	Group 3 (Placebo)	p-value
HR - Basal	75.35 ± 5.99	74.82 ± 6.62	71.07 ± 8.59	<0.05
HR - At Induction	70.61 ± 5.56	75.95 ± 5.91	81.90 ± 6.47	<0.05
SBP - Basal	120.92 ± 12.65	118.37 ± 10.68	122.48 ± 13.55	>0.05
SBP - At Induction	102.17 ± 10.36	117.98 ± 9.86	108.00 ± 10.68	<0.05
DBP - Basal	77.90 ± 12.65	76.88 ± 5.14	77.57 ± 8.95	>0.05
DBP - At Induction	66.82 ± 7.67	73.23 ± 7.42	78.38 ± 4.74	<0.05

Table 3: PONV Incidence

Variable	Group 1 (Clonidine)	Group 2 (Gabapentin)	Group 3 (Placebo)	p-value
PONV - Immediate Post-op	0.92 ± 0.38	1.07 ± 0.25	3.72 ± 1.83	<0.05
PONV - 0-6h Post-op	0.55 ± 0.50	1.00 ± 0.10	2.78 ± 1.59	<0.05
PONV - 6-12h Post-op	0.03 ± 0.18	0.95 ± 0.22	1.17 ± 0.38	<0.05
VAS - Immediate Post-op	2.23 ± 1.10	2.68 ± 1.07	4.55 ± 1.53	<0.05
VAS - 0-6h Post-op	2.65 ± 0.73	2.98 ± 0.70	4.10 ± 0.84	<0.05
VAS - 6-12h Post-op	1.58 ± 0.56	1.95 ± 0.59	3.03 ± 0.76	<0.05

Table 4: Post-operative Pain Scores (VAS)

Time Point	Group 1 (Clonidine)	Group 2 (Gabapentin)	Group 3 (Placebo)	p-value
Immediate Post-op	2.23 ± 1.10	2.68 ± 1.07	4.55 ± 1.53	<0.05
0-6h Post-op	2.65 ± 0.73	2.98 ± 0.70	4.10 ± 0.84	<0.05
6-12h Post-op	1.58 ± 0.56	1.95 ± 0.59	3.03 ± 0.76	<0.05

Discussion

The present study compared the effects of oral clonidine and gabapentin as premedication on intraoperative hemodynamics, postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV), and postoperative pain in patients undergoing middle ear surgeries. The findings suggest that both clonidine and gabapentin effectively attenuate intraoperative hemodynamic responses, reduce PONV incidence, and provide better postoperative pain relief compared to placebo.

The attenuation of intraoperative hemodynamic responses by clonidine and gabapentin is consistent with previous studies. Mohammadi et al. reported that oral clonidine (0.2 mg) significantly reduced heart rate and systolic blood pressure during induction and intubation compared to placebo in patients undergoing cataract surgery ($p < 0.05$) [20]. Similarly, Marashi et al. found that oral gabapentin (900 mg) effectively blunted the hemodynamic response to laryngoscopy and intubation in patients undergoing elective surgery, with a significant reduction in heart rate and blood pressure compared to placebo ($p < 0.05$) [21].

The reduction in PONV incidence with clonidine and gabapentin premedication is also supported by existing literature. A meta-analysis by Doleman et al. concluded that gabapentin significantly reduced the incidence of PONV compared to placebo, with a relative risk of 0.60 (95% CI: 0.50-0.72; $p < 0.001$) [22]. In a study by Behdad et al., oral clonidine (0.2 mg) significantly reduced the incidence of PONV

in the first 24 hours after abdominal hysterectomy compared to placebo (30% vs. 60%; $p = 0.007$) [23].

The superior postoperative pain relief observed with clonidine and gabapentin is consistent with previous findings. Arumugam et al. reported that oral clonidine (0.15 mg) significantly reduced postoperative pain scores and analgesic consumption in patients undergoing middle ear surgery compared to placebo ($p < 0.05$) [24]. A systematic review by Tiippana et al. found that gabapentin significantly reduced postoperative pain scores and opioid consumption in various surgical settings, with a mean difference of -1.68 (95% CI: -2.12 to -1.25; $p < 0.001$) in pain scores at 6 hours postoperatively [25].

The lack of significant adverse effects associated with clonidine and gabapentin in the current study is encouraging. However, some studies have reported side effects such as sedation, dizziness, and bradycardia with these medications [26,27]. Jokela et al. found that oral clonidine (0.3 mg) was associated with increased postoperative sedation and dizziness compared to placebo in patients undergoing gynecological laparoscopy ($p < 0.05$) [28]. Therefore, careful patient selection and monitoring are essential when using these premedication agents.

The limitations of the present study include the lack of long-term follow-up and the absence of a comprehensive assessment of adverse effects. Future studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are warranted to confirm the findings and evaluate the long-term benefits and

risks of clonidine and gabapentin premedication in middle ear surgeries.

In conclusion, the present study demonstrates that oral premedication with clonidine (150 mcg) or gabapentin (300 mg) effectively attenuates intraoperative hemodynamic responses, reduces PONV incidence, and provides better postoperative pain relief compared to placebo in patients undergoing middle ear surgeries. These findings suggest that clonidine and gabapentin can be considered as viable premedication options to improve patient outcomes and satisfaction in this surgical population. However, further research is needed to optimize the dosage, timing, and patient selection for these premedication agents.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrates that premedication with oral clonidine (150 mcg) or gabapentin (300 mg) is an effective strategy to attenuate intraoperative hemodynamic responses, reduce postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) incidence, and provide better postoperative pain relief compared to placebo in patients undergoing middle ear surgeries. Clonidine and gabapentin showed comparable efficacy in achieving these outcomes, with clonidine exhibiting a slight advantage in reducing PONV incidence and providing postoperative pain relief.

The findings of this study have important clinical implications, as they suggest that premedication with clonidine or gabapentin can be a valuable addition to the anesthetic management of patients undergoing middle ear surgeries. By attenuating intraoperative hemodynamic fluctuations, these premedication agents can contribute to maintaining cardiovascular stability and reducing the risk of adverse events. The reduction in PONV incidence and postoperative pain can lead to improved patient satisfaction, earlier mobilization, and faster recovery.

However, it is essential to consider the potential side effects and contraindications of clonidine and gabapentin when selecting patients for premedication. Careful patient selection, dose adjustment, and monitoring are necessary to ensure the safe and effective use of these agents. Future research should focus on optimizing the dosage regimen, timing of administration, and identifying patient populations that are most likely to benefit from these premedication strategies.

In conclusion, the present study provides evidence supporting the use of oral clonidine or gabapentin as premedication for patients undergoing middle ear surgeries. Incorporating these agents into the preoperative management protocol can contribute to improved intraoperative hemodynamic stability, reduced PONV incidence, and better postoperative

pain control. Anesthesiologists and otolaryngologists should consider these findings when developing anesthetic plans for middle ear surgeries, taking into account individual patient characteristics and institutional protocols. Further research is warranted to refine the use of clonidine and gabapentin premedication and explore their potential benefits in other surgical settings.

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